

Characterization of ultrathin nickel films deposited by thermal laser evaporation

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Thermal laser evaporation is a physical vapor deposition technique of increasing interest because of its ability to evaporate essentially any solid element, even the most refractory such as W. However, many films deposited by this method, especially non-epitaxial films, remain to be characterized; further, key system components such as the laser delivery system have not been described in detail. Here, we present the evaporation and characterization of ultrathin nickel films deposited with a home-built thermal laser evaporation system. The system employs a continuous-wave 1 kW fiber laser (1070 nm) focused to sub-millimeter diameter onto a nickel target rod mounted inside an ultrahigh-vacuum chamber. The laser heats the target to a temperature high enough to produce vapor for film deposition; for Ni, this temperature is around the melting point of 1725 K. We report the characterization of the surface roughness, composition, and room-temperature electrical properties of the films along with the design of the major components of our system. This work advances the growing consensus regarding the potential of thermal laser evaporation for thin film deposition and epitaxy and provides the necessary design information to facilitate broader adoption of the technique.

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Physical vapor deposition (PVD) of thin films is performed by various well-established techniques, including thermal and electron beam evaporation (e-beam), sputtering, pulsed laser deposition (PLD), and others.¹ Evaporative methods rely on the condensation of vapor created by heating of source material onto a substrate. Sputtering and PLD are non-equilibrium techniques based on the ejection of material from a target by plasma ion impingement and the ablation of a target with energetic laser pulses, respectively. These techniques enable directional or conformal deposition of diverse elemental and compound materials.

Film deposition by evaporation is in routine use, for instance for deposition of metals for devices and for epitaxial growth using molecular beam epitaxy (MBE). However, evaporation of refractory elements is a long-standing challenge owing to their low vapor pressure. For instance, elements like W, Ru, Nb, Ta, and Mo cannot be deposited using effusion cells, and while e-beam evaporation is technically possible, the deposition rates are usually well below 1 Å/sec. Additionally, careful monitoring and preparation are required to avoid damaging the evaporation system due to the required high powers and temperatures.

The use of continuous-wave lasers to thermally evaporate source material for deposition has potential to overcome these limitations.²⁻⁵ In recent years, this technique has been termed thermal laser evaporation⁵⁻⁸ (TLE) following earlier works which termed it variations of laser evaporation^{3,9-16}. The technique has also been called thermal laser epitaxy¹⁷⁻²⁴, which is also abbreviated TLE. In this work, we take TLE to mean thermal laser evaporation as the deposited films here are non-epitaxial. TLE uses continuous-wave (CW) lasers focused onto freestanding targets (slugs or crucibles) to provide the necessary thermal energy to produce vapor for deposition. It differs from PLD (or laser-MBE) in that heating is performed using CW rather than pulsed lasers, leading to deposition by thermal evaporation rather than an ablation process.^{3,25,26} The quasi-stationary nature of the deposition makes the deposition process more similar to thermal PVD techniques like e-beam evaporation. TLE requires no crucible for many materials, allowing for the deposition of both refractory metals and elements that may react with a crucible. Because the energy source is located outside of vacuum, the technique is especially suitable for reactive evaporation since there are no hot filaments or resistive heaters that could be degraded by exposure to process gases (e.g. O₂)⁴. Finally, the source-substrate distance is typically an order of magnitude smaller than in e-beam evaporation or MBE, allowing for higher pressures of reactive background

gases without scattering the metallic vapors.

TLE was initially developed contemporaneously with MBE, electron-beam evaporation, and PLD in the late 1960s. A variety of oxides and compounds were deposited using TLE^{2,3}, as well as pure elements including C^{10,27}, Os²⁸, Pt²⁹, and Te³⁰. However, laser technology of the time was inadequate for TLE to compete with other techniques due to two difficulties. First, the most practical CW laser of the time was the CO₂ laser, which was then limited in power to a few hundred watts³⁰. Further, its 10.6 μm wavelength is not well absorbed by metals, leading many investigators to focus on oxide or compound targets^{3,31}. Second, the coating of optical elements exposed to the heated target added complexity to the energy delivery system compared to effusion cells or electron beam systems⁴. Although this latter drawback could be partially worked around by using mirrors and apertures^{4,12,30}, the other techniques were technically simpler to implement.

Due in large part to the maturation of other PVD techniques, TLE was neglected for decades. Recent developments in laser technology, however, have made the technique increasingly viable. The key development has been the commercial availability of high-power fiber lasers, which emit at micron wavelengths and feature output powers up to multiple kilowatts. Fiber lasers are more useful than the CO₂ laser for evaporating most elements due to the order of magnitude higher absorption of metals at around 1 micron compared to 10.6 microns³¹. Recently, a group at the Max Planck Institute at Stuttgart has developed a modern implementation of TLE using high-power CW fiber lasers and deposited many elements, oxides, and nitrides.^{5-8,19,32} However, modern TLE has only been performed by one group to date, and many of the details of key system components such as the beam delivery system have not been reported. Further, although the deposition of nearly all solid, nonradioactive elements has been reported, the characterization of the non-epitaxial films has been limited to only a few cross-sectional SEM images^{5,6,19}. Whether TLE can produce non-epitaxial films which meet or exceed the characteristics of those deposited by traditional PVD techniques such as sputtering and electron beam evaporation has not yet been determined.

Here, we report the deposition of ultrathin Ni films using a home-built TLE system employing a 1 kW CW fiber laser with a 1070 nm wavelength. A deposition rate of 0.35 $\text{\AA}/\text{sec}$ was achieved with 177 W of CW laser power. The deposited film was 14.7 ± 0.1 nm thick and exhibited RMS roughness $R_q = 1.10 \pm 0.14$ nm. The electrical resistivity,

FIG. 1 (A) Photograph of the TLE system at Caltech. At the top left is the laser delivery system, and to its right is the bellows mounted to the substrate holder. Around the center from the left to right are a RHEED system, QCM, and shutter control, respectively. At bottom are the RGA and two bellows to which the target holders are mounted. (B) Rendering of the fiber laser delivery system. 1. Kinematic laser mount 2. Laser collimator 3. Lenses 4. Thermocouple 5. Water cooled mirror mount 6. Mirror 7. Laser window.

known to be a sensitive probe of the quality of electrically-conducting films, was measured to be $22 \pm 0.2 \mu\Omega \text{ cm}$, in quantitative agreement with the best prior value reported for Ni films of a similar thickness. We also provide an overview of the system design and discuss design considerations for key system components such as the beam delivery system. This work indicates that TLE-deposited films are of equal quality to the best films made by other evaporation methods, and the provided system design details will enable broader adoption of the technique, advancing the science and practice of thin film deposition.

We begin by presenting the details of our home-built TLE system. A photograph of the system is shown in Fig. 1(a). It consists of a water-cooled vacuum chamber (Kurt J. Lesker Hydra Cool™) with a turbopump providing a base pressure below 10^{-9} Torr. Inside the chamber are a target holder and substrate holder, which are both mounted on bellows to enable target alignment and sample transfer. The chamber is also equipped with a quartz-crystal microbalance (Telemark) for deposition rate monitoring and a residual gas analyzer (SRS RGA200) to monitor the vacuum conditions.

The laser delivery system is shown in Fig. 1(b). The laser is a 1 kW fiber laser (IPG Photonics, YLR-1000-WC) and terminates in a water-cooled free-space coupler and colli-

mator (IPG, D30 F100 AC HLC-8), which is mounted in a kinematic laser mount to enable fine beam alignment. Two C-coated lenses (Thorlabs LA1301-C-ML and LC1093-C-ML) are used to focus the beam to sub-millimeter diameter on the target. This beam diameter was selected to ensure that the melt pool is contained within the target, ideally avoiding unpredictable angular variations of the specularly reflected beam. The diameter is slightly smaller than that used in other TLE works (c.f. 1.1mm¹⁹). An antireflective window is used to pass the beam into vacuum (Lesker VPZL-275LYAG). The final optical element is an aluminum off-axis parabolic mirror (Edmund Optics 35-590) mounted on a water-cooled rotatable flange. Pt paste (Tanaka Kikinokoku TR-7091T) is used to enhance thermal contact between the flange and the mirror. A type K thermocouple is placed in contact with the mirror to monitor its temperature. A water cooled beam dump is placed in the path of the beam specularly reflected by the target.

With this optical configuration, it was found that the deposition could be performed for around 45 minutes while limiting the mirror temperature to below 100 °C. The mirror temperature steadily increased with time due to thermal resistance from the mirror surface to the water-cooled mounting flange and an increase in film absorbance due to deposition from the target. These issues can be mitigated by water-cooling the backside of a thin (~ 2 - 4 mm) mirror and use of a pinhole aperture to minimize deposition. These modifications are the focus of ongoing work but were not used in this study.

The target and its mounting structure are shown in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b). The target in this work consists of a 12.7 mm long, 6.35 mm diameter Ni rod (Lesker, 99.995%) which was machined down to 3.13 mm at the base to minimize the thermal conductance to the target holder. We chose Ni for this work to facilitate comparison of electrical data in the literature and because it is less technically challenging to evaporate compared to the refractory elements. Although Ni was primarily chosen for experimental convenience, our findings may be applicable to other metal films, including refractory elements, for which thermal evaporation remains difficult. TLE of refractory elements using our system will be reported in a future publication.

The target is mounted in a press-fit slot within a molybdenum cantilever, and a type-C thermocouple is mounted under the target to monitor the temperature. This cantilever design was chosen to allow for target insertion through a DN40CF flange. We note that without active cooling, the cantilever can become hot enough during deposition that oxida-

tion would be expected if reactive gases such as oxygen were present. In the present case, deposition was performed in vacuum so that this issue is irrelevant; however, future designs will incorporate water cooling of the target holder.

The substrate and its holder are shown in Fig. 2(c). A $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ sapphire substrate (University Wafer, C-plane, SSP) is mounted on a home-built molybdenum disk that suspends the sample upside down $\sim 76 \text{ mm}$ above the target. The disk is suspended by steel fingers that are mounted to a cantilever suspended by steel rods from a flange fitted onto an adjustable bellows. Although this design is attractive for simplicity, it does not permit sample rotation. Future implementations will employ a fully concentric design to facilitate sample rotation. The substrate was cleaned by rinsing with acetone, isopropanol, and deionized water. Substrate heating was not performed in this study, but it is under active development using CO_2 laser heating as discussed in Ref. 33. It is expected that substrate heating will result in higher crystallinity and lower oxygen and carbon contamination.

The deposition procedure consisted of the following steps. First, the system was pumped down to a base pressure below 10^{-9} Torr. No chamber bakeout was performed. A Ti shutter on a linear translation stage covered the sample for the entire process until deposition was initiated. The laser power was held between 119 and 144 W for approximately an hour to bake out adsorbed gases from the target and its holder. After the pressure stabilized around 10^{-7} Torr, the power was steadily increased until a steady-state deposition rate was measured in the QCM. The shutter was then opened to allow deposition. For the present study, the deposition rate was $0.35 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$.

During deposition, flux instabilities (second timescales) and slower variations (minute timescales) were observed. These effects have been previously reported and are discussed in Ref. 19. The faster deposition rate fluctuations had a magnitude of around 3.6% (as measured by QCM). Although no mechanism for these fluctuations has been established at this time, possible mitigation strategies include rastering¹⁹ and defocusing the beam to increase the effective evaporation area at the target surface. The slower, larger flux variations can be attributed to a decrease in the mirror reflectivity as Ni was deposited on the mirror. We did not employ any power compensation to mitigate this effect. During our depositions, the rate decrease owing to nickel deposition on the mirror was no more than 10% over any run.

We next present qualitative features of the deposition process. Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) show

FIG. 2 (A) Target holder apparatus, with thermocouple routed within the interior. 1. Steel tube 2. Aluminum flange adapter 3. C-type thermocouple feedthrough. (B) Target holder cantilever, with thermocouple routed underneath. 4. Titanium screw used as a hinge 5. Steel cantilever support 6. Titanium screws 7. Molybdenum cantilever, with cut outs to increase conduction path between target and screws, and a press-fit hole drilled for the target 8. Target. (C) Substrate holder. 9. Conflat flange 10. Steel rods 11. Nuts and washers to mount the cantilever 12. High-temperature steel fingers 13. Molybdenum substrate disk 14. Molybdenum strips 15. Substrate chip.

images of the Ni target before and after deposition, respectively. The remnants of the melt pool formed during deposition can be observed in Fig. 3(b). The deposition rate measured by QCM versus inverse laser power is shown in Fig. 3(c). To account for the geometric factor from the positioning of the QCM relative to the sample, the measured rates were scaled to match the measured film thickness. The deposition rate exhibits the expected Arrhenius dependence on laser power^{6,19}, with a power of 202 W yielding a deposition rate of 0.98 Å/sec.

FIG. 3 Photograph of the nickel target mounted in the chamber (A) before deposition and (B) after deposition. A red guide laser is on in both images. Before deposition, the laser is observable from the camera due to diffuse reflections from the surface before melting. After deposition, the guide beam is not visible due to the increased specularity of the melt pool. (C) Deposition rate measured by QCM versus inverse laser power (symbols) and a fit line. Present data (red circles) shown along with data by Ref. 19 (green triangles). The present data follow an Arrhenius relationship: Rate [$\text{\AA}/\text{s}$] = $4064 \exp(-1673/P[\text{W}])$.

We note that the observed deposition rate was lower than that previously published in Ref. 19, which concluded that higher energy densities will increase the deposition rate. Because our laser was focused tighter than it was in the reference but yielded lower deposition rates, it is likely that the assumption that conduction does not play a major role is invalid in our setup. Because our target is pressed into the holder, conductive heat loss from the target is sufficient to heat the holder to well above $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as indicated by the orange color of blackbody radiation. Because conductive heat loss is linear while radiation and evaporative loss vary more strongly with temperature difference, conductive loss will be most pronounced at lower temperatures, which may be the reason the difference between data sets is most significant at lower powers. This finding highlights the necessity of minimizing thermal contact if the efficiency of evaporation at low powers is a concern.

Next, we examine the physical characteristics and surface morphology of the films. The film thickness was measured using ex-situ ellipsometry on a J.A. Woollam M2000 with the

FIG. 4 AFM scan of the film surface. (A) 500×500 nm scan (256 lines, 0.3 Hz) and (B) 2×2 μm scan (256 lines, 0.5 Hz). The RMS roughness $R_q = 1.10 \pm 0.14$ nm.

built-in profiles for sapphire and nickel. The measurement yielded a value of 14.7 ± 0.1 nm, which was not changed by incorporating roughness or native oxide. This value is quantitatively consistent with step height measurement via atomic-force microscopy (AFM) performed on a step formed by the substrate holder. The film surface morphology was characterized using a Bruker Dimension Icon AFM in PeakForce Tapping mode with a ScanAsyst-Air probe. The AFM scans of the sample are presented in Fig. 4. The scans indicate that the sample exhibits the smoothness expected of a thermally evaporated thin metal film growing by nucleation and coalescence, with RMS roughness $R_q = 1.10 \pm 0.14$ nm.³⁴

The chemical composition of the film was characterized using x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The measurement was performed using a Kratos Axis Ultra XPS using an Al K α source and used an ion mill for depth profiling. The surface XPS spectrum is shown in Fig. 5(a), and the composition throughout depth profiling in Fig. 5(b). The detected elements were nickel with some amount of oxygen and carbon. The oxygen content ranges from approximately 0.6% to 2% in the bulk, while the carbon content ranges from about 7% to 12%. We attribute the carbon content to the adventitious carbon that remained on the sapphire substrate prior to deposition, which diffused into the film as a result of indirect heating of the substrate by the hot target during the deposition process. This adventitious

FIG. 5 (A) XPS spectrum of the nickel film surface. Oxygen, carbon, and nickel peak locations are shown according to the Kratos element library. (B) XPS compositional analysis with depth profiling. Detected elements include nickel (blue circles), oxygen (orange triangles), carbon (magenta diamonds), and aluminum (green squares). After 150 s of milling the film becomes thin enough that the underlying sapphire substrate begins to appear in the XPS signal. Error bars represent the area uncertainty reported by CASA XPS.

carbon may also be responsible for a portion of the oxygen content. No other elements were found within the detection limit of $\sim 0.2\%$. In a future work, secondary ion mass spectrometry will be employed to better characterize the concentrations of trace impurities.

Finally, the electrical resistivity was measured using the van der Pauw method (vdP). The resistivity of thin films is well-known to be a sensitive probe of the structural quality and chemical purity of electrical conductors, and data is readily available in the literature for Ni. Wirebonding was performed using Al wires with a Westbond 7476D Wire Bonder, and the vdP measurement was performed using a Keithley 2400 SourceMeter. At room temperature, the value was measured as $22.0 \pm 0.2 \mu\Omega\text{cm}$. Fig. 6 plots this value along with other values for Ni films of varying thickness from prior studies. It is observed that the measured value is compatible with those reported for films of a similar thickness by Ref. 35, which utilized magnetron sputtering. The resistivity is approximately 33% lower than the best measurement of thermally evaporated ultra-thin nickel (to our knowledge) by Ref. 36. We conclude that the deposited films are of comparable quality to films deposited using conventional PVD techniques like e-beam evaporation and sputtering. Future work will characterize the temperature-dependence of the resistivity and the residual resistance ratio

FIG. 6 Electrical resistivity versus film thickness at room temperature. The measurement from this work is indicated as the red point (thickness of 147 Å), and the uncertainty is smaller than the symbol. Referenced data from Ref. 36 (blue triangles) and Ref. 35 (green squares).

for films grown via multiple PVD methods to gain further insight into the structural quality and chemical purity, as well as demonstrate deposition of other elements and compounds by TLE in our system.

In summary, we have reported the deposition and characterization of ultrathin Ni films using a home-built thermal laser evaporation system. The successful demonstration of a modern implementation of TLE is the first to be reported in the United States. This work also provides details of the system design, and the first analysis of roughness, composition, and resistivity for a TLE-deposited non-epitaxial metal film. The films exhibit smoothness consistent with that expected of thin metallic films and electrical resistivity on par with those of films deposited by other PVD techniques. Our work adds to the growing consensus regarding the promising potential of TLE for deposition of high-quality films and compounds, molecular beam epitaxy, and related applications.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

REFERENCES

- ¹D. M. Mattox, *Handbook of Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) Processing*, 2nd ed. (Elsevier Science, Oxford, UK, 2010).
- ²G. Groh, [Journal of Applied Physics](#) **39**, 5804 (1968).
- ³J. T. Cheung and H. Sankur, [Critical Reviews in Solid State and Materials Sciences](#) **15**, 63 (1988).
- ⁴H. Sankur and J. T. Cheung, [Applied Physics A](#) **47**, 271 (1988).
- ⁵W. Braun and J. Mannhart, [AIP Advances](#) **9**, 085310 (2019).
- ⁶T. J. Smart, J. Mannhart, and W. Braun, [Journal of Laser Applications](#) **33**, 022008 (2021).
- ⁷D. Y. Kim, J. Mannhart, and W. Braun, [APL Materials](#) **9**, 081105 (2021).
- ⁸D. Y. Kim, T. J. Smart, L. Majer, S. Smink, J. Mannhart, and W. Braun, [Journal of Applied Physics](#) **132**, 245110 (2022).
- ⁹V. S. Ban and D. A. Kramer, [Journal of Materials Science](#) **5**, 978 (1970).

- ¹⁰S. Fujimori, *Shinkū* **23**, 333 (1980).
- ¹¹H. Sankur and J. T. Cheung, *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A* **1**, 1806 (1983).
- ¹²H. Sankur and R. Hall, *Appl. Opt.* **24**, 3343 (1985).
- ¹³B. Brauns, D. Schäfer, R. Wolf, and G. Zscherpe, *Optica Acta: International Journal of Optics* **33**, 545 (1986).
- ¹⁴X. Yin, G. Lai, J. Chen, and J. Kao, *Surface and Coatings Technology* **90**, 239 (1997).
- ¹⁵S. Mineta, M. Kohata, N. Yasunaga, and Y. Kikuta, *Thin Solid Films* **189**, 125 (1990).
- ¹⁶N. P. Jasti, S. Tirosh, A. Halder, E. Teblum, and D. Cahen, *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A* **42**, 043406 (2024).
- ¹⁷A. Al Taleb, L. N. Majer, E. W. Selfors, S. Smink, B. Holst, J. Mannhart, W. Braun, and D. Farías, *Thin Solid Films* **758**, 139449 (2022).
- ¹⁸T. J. Smart, F. V. E. Hensling, D. Y. Kim, L. N. Majer, Y. E. Suyolcu, D. Dereh, D. G. Schlom, D. Jena, J. Mannhart, and W. Braun, *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A* **41**, 042701 (2023).
- ¹⁹T. J. Smart, *Thermal Laser Epitaxy: From Fundamental Physics to the Growth of Novel Thin Films*, Ph.D. thesis, University of Stuttgart (2023).
- ²⁰D. Y. Kim, T. J. Smart, J. Mannhart, and W. Braun, *Crystal Growth & Design* **23**, 8087 (2023).
- ²¹T. J. Smart, D. Y. Kim, and W. Braun, *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology B* **42**, 062204 (2024).
- ²²L. N. Majer, S. Smink, W. Braun, H. Wang, P. A. van Aken, J. Mannhart, and F. V. E. Hensling, *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A* **42**, 052702 (2024).
- ²³L. N. Majer, S. Smink, W. Braun, B. Fenk, V. Harbola, B. Stuhlhofer, H. Wang, P. A. van Aken, J. Mannhart, and F. V. E. Hensling, *APL Materials* **12**, 091108 (2024).
- ²⁴T. J. Smart, B. E. Abali, H. Boschker, and W. Braun, *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* **58**, 205303 (2025).
- ²⁵R. Gross, J. Klein, B. Wiedenhorst, C. Hoefener, U. Schoop, J. B. Philipp, M. Schonecke, F. Herbstritt, L. Alff, Y. Lu, A. Marx, S. Schymon, S. Thienhaus, and W. Mader, in *Superconducting and Related Oxides: Physics and Nanoengineering IV*, Vol. 4058, edited by D. Pavuna and I. Bozovic, International Society for Optics and Photonics (SPIE, 2000) pp. 278 – 294.

- ²⁶D. H. Lowndes, D. B. Geohegan, A. A. Puretzky, D. P. Norton, and C. M. Rouleau, [Science](#) **273**, 898 (1996).
- ²⁷S. Fujimori, T. Kasai, and T. Inamura, [Thin Solid Films](#) **92**, 71 (1982).
- ²⁸P. Maier-Komor, [Nuclear Instruments and Methods](#) **167**, 73 (1979).
- ²⁹M. S. Hess and J. F. Milkosky, [Journal of Applied Physics](#) **43**, 4680 (1972).
- ³⁰G. Hass and J. B. Ramsey, [Appl. Opt.](#) **8**, 1115 (1969).
- ³¹W. W. Duley, *Laser Processing and Analysis of Materials*, 1st ed. (Plenum Press, 1983).
- ³²D. Y. Kim, V. Harbola, S. Jung, J. Lee, S. Roy, F. V. E. Hensling, L. N. Majer, H. Wang, P. A. van Aken, J. M. J. Lopes, N. Aggarwal, J. Mannhart, and W. Braun, [APL Materials](#) **13**, 011125 (2025).
- ³³W. Braun, M. Jäger, G. Laskin, P. Ngabonziza, W. Voesch, P. Wittlich, and J. Mannhart, [APL Materials](#) **8**, 071112 (2020).
- ³⁴D. Pashley, [Advances in Physics](#) **14**, 327 (1965).
- ³⁵S. Giurgola, A. Rodriguez, L. Martinez, P. Vergani, F. Lucchi, S. Benchabane, and V. Pruneri, [Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics](#) **20**, 181 (2009).
- ³⁶M. Angadi and L. Udachan, [Thin Solid Films](#) **79**, 149 (1981).